

The effect of the motivations of teachers who are working in the institution far from their residence address on their professional and private lives

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Abstract. In this research, the effect of the motivation of teachers who had a long distance between their institution and their residence addresses and who travelled daily on their professional and private lives were studied. In the research, the problems of the teachers who worked in the district of Döşemealtı in Antalya province and who could not reside in the district of Döşemealtı due to different reasons were interpreted. Most of the teachers who participated in the interview stated that they experienced physical and mental distress while reaching the institutions where they worked, and that the effects made their lives difficult both materially and spiritually. Spending a lot of time in traffic while travelling, having the risk of having an accident on the road, having to be on the road in adverse weather conditions, waking up too early to reach their institutions, not having breakfast because they had to leave too early, not spending quality time with their children in their family life due to working hours. It was understood that not being able to spare time outside of school affected teachers negatively. It was found that the reasons why the teachers did not reside in the district of Döşemealtı included the fact that their spouses' workplace was in the center, the educational status of their children, and the health institutions in the center were more diverse. It was seen that the travelling teachers had financial problems at first, and it was foreseen that the problems could be partially solved by making changes in the assignment and relocation regulations, providing service opportunities or giving a travel allowance in addition to their salaries in order to solve these problems.

Keywords: Teachers, motivation, stress, distance, professional and individual characteristics

Introduction

Teachers, who have an important place in society, are affected by many institutions, individuals and legal regulations. Teachers are expected to perform important tasks such as arranging the learning environment and guiding students (Orakçı, 2005). Accordingly, it is seen that the most important factor in the MoNE (Ministry Of National Education) vision is the teacher. Therefore, in order to keep teachers' motivation at a high level and increase their productivity, it is necessary to eliminate or minimize their non-educational problems (Çetin, 2006).

The region where teachers work, environmental conditions and expectation levels are the factors that can cause stress (Avşaroğlu, Deniz & Kahraman, 2005). As a result of the stress experienced, it is inevitable that teachers' sincerity and compassion towards their students, their profession and other people may be negatively affected, and it is inevitable that they will experience difficulties in fulfilling their responsibilities and values as a profession (Kayabaşı, 2008).

Being a teacher is a profession that requires great responsibility when considered in general. In Turkey, while the different problems of teachers continue, the problems of teachers working in rural areas become more disturbing (Özdemir, 2000).

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Teachers are first appointed as candidate teachers according to the regulation of the Ministry of National Education. According to this regulation, teachers were evaluated as candidate teachers in the first year of their profession and were subjected to candidate teacher seminars. Instead, today, teachers are evaluated by evaluators three times in total, once in the first term and twice in the second term. The persons who will make the evaluation consist of the education inspector appointed by the provincial national education directorates, the director of the institution where the novice teacher works, and the advisor teacher determined by the principal in the institution where the novice teacher works. The first evaluation is carried out individually by the principal and the advisor teacher in the institution where the teacher works. The second assessment is applied in the same way as the first assessment. The third evaluation is carried out by the education inspector, school principal and advisor teacher by filling in different forms individually. Finally, candidate teachers who are unsuccessful in performance evaluation lose their right to be a candidate teacher and are terminated from their civil service (Resmi Gazete, 2015).

According to the 19th article of the Ministry of National Education, the appointment of teachers by relocation includes the following; displacements due to disability, compulsory labor obligation, displacements as a requirement of service, displacements due to emergency situations, displacements of national team trainers and national athletes, displacements due to field changes, displacements of surplus teachers. In this regulation, it is emphasized that the norm staff gap and service point superiority are required while applying the principles of displacement. In addition, it has been stated that teachers whose nominations are canceled can apply for the appointment of an excuse group in certain periods (January-August) every year. (Resmi Gazete, 2015)

According to The Turkish Language Association (**TDK**), the word residence means to live in a place (TDK, 2022). Residence means to settle in the place in question, to be a resident of a certain place. There are no legal restrictions regarding the residence of teachers in their place of residence according to the Civil Servants Law 657' (DMK -Devlet Memurları Kanunu- No. 657). In addition, considering the statement "Everyone has the freedom to settle and travel" in Article 23 of the binding Constitution titled "freedom of residence and travel", there is no provision that obliges civil servants to reside at the place of duty. There is no relevant provision (DMK No. 657).

In Turkey, the principles determined by the Ministry of National Education are adhered to in the appointment and placement of teachers, but this system has some limitations. One of the main problems affecting teachers is the distance between the institution where the teachers work and their residence addresses. This problem causes teachers to work miles away from their residential address and travel every day. Teachers working in places far from their residence addresses make requests to be assigned to their residence areas, but these requests are often not fulfilled.

The goals that people set for themselves always keep their motivation high. 'Motivation, which is defined as the processes that activate the individual and direct the behavior in the desired direction and in line with the goals of the organization' (Yıldırım, 2007). It is very important in ensuring that the organization reaches the desired goal with a good performance of the employees (Altinkurt, Yılmaz & Erol, 2014). It is one of the most important elements in increasing the success of the school and the student that teachers carry out their work with motivation.

The fact that teachers cannot work in the regions where they have their own residence addresses causes their motivation to decrease for many reasons. For example, a breastfed baby needs his mother during the day, especially during feeding hours (Resmi Gazete, 2013). Therefore, the law supports teacher mothers to feed their babies under the name of 'maternity leave' until the baby reaches a certain age. However, due to the distance from her home of the institution where she works, most of this mother's time is spent on the road to reach home. This situation creates psychological distress in the mother and causes a lack of motivation both in her profession and in her private life.

In the literature review, the physical and psychological problems and general problems of teachers working in villages or districts were mentioned. In this context, no articles, dissertations or doctoral studies have

been found about the individual and professional motivations of teachers who are too far from their place of residence and the institution they work for. It is hoped that this study will contribute to the literature review besides being original in this respect.

What is the effect of the motivations of the teachers whose residence address is far from the institution they work in, on their professional and private lives? For this purpose answers to following questions were sought to answer:

1. What are the teachers' views on the factors affecting their motivation?
2. What are the reasons why teachers prefer the institution they are currently working in?
3. What are the opinions of the teachers about the difficulties experienced in transportation to the institution where they are currently working?
4. What are the teachers' views on the change in their eating habits?
5. What are the teachers' views on the effect of working in a distant place on their family life?
6. What are the teachers' views on the effect of working in a distant place on their professional life?
7. What are the opinions of teachers about whether working in a distant place financially affects the family budget?
8. What are the views of teachers on the subject of working in a distant place and allocating time for extracurricular activities?

Method and paradigm of research

The knowledge constitute interest of this research was practical and the paradigm of this research was interpretive as it was subjective and intersubjective views of the individuals (Gunbayi & Sorm, 2018, Gunbayi & Sorm, 2020; Gunbayi, 2020 a,b).

This research was carried out with the descriptive phenomenology (phenomenology) design used in qualitative research methods. Phenomenology study contributes to understanding and interpreting the meanings that individuals create in their minds by focusing on how individuals perceive reality and their experiences regarding these perceptions (Creswell, 1998; Patton, 1990, Polkhorne, 1989)

Sampling

The sample of this study consisted of the teachers who lived in Antalya city center, whose institution was in the district of Döşemealtı, and who had to travel 20-40 km every day, selected via purposive sampling method and convenient sampling technique (Palys, 2008). The teachers were in the same schools. Three of the participants were subject teachers and the other was vice principal.

Table 1.

Distribution of demographic variables of the participants

Participant	Gender	Age	Marital Status	Number of children	Seniority	Start year	The duration of travel
A	Man	36	Married	1	15 years	2021	1 year
B	Man	43	Married	2	12 years	2017	5 years
C	Woman	47	Married	2	12 years	2015	6 years
D	Woman	36	Married	1	12 years	2018	5 years

Data collection

In the research, data were collected through individual face to face interview with semi-structured form, which consisted of main and probe questions prepared by the researcher. Before the questions were prepared, a literature review was conducted on the subject. In addition to individual interviews, focus group interviews were also carried out. The interviews were recorded, and the interviewee was informed about this before the recording was made.

Ethical procedures

Scientific research ethics were followed at all stages of the research: (1) Ethics Committee Approval of this research was obtained from Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the meeting of 14 decision numbered 377 on November 4th, 2021 (2) permission was obtained from the Antalya Provincial Directorate of National Education for the research and (3) an informed consent form was obtained from the participants before the interview. (4) Participants were informed that their names would not be mentioned under any circumstances in the study and that they would be given the sequential code A, B, C, D.

Validity and reliability of the research

In order to increase the internal and external validity and reliability based on the criteria of credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability, (Lincoln and Guba, 1985) of the qualitative data, followings were carried out: (1) in order to increase the internal validity (credibility) of the research, an interview form was developed by the review of the relevant literature (2) in order to increase the external validity (transferability) of the research, a purposive sampling method was chosen based on voluntarism to get opinions and experiences (3) in order to increase the internal reliability (confirmability) of the research Cohen's kappa coefficient was calculated to determine inter-rater reliability of themes as 0.83, , a perfect level of agreement between the coding d) in order to increase the external reliability (dependability) of the research, all data collected were kept to prove on demand (Landis and Koach, 1977; Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Cohen, Mannion and Morrison, 2007, Gunbayi, 2018).

Data analysis

In order to increase the reliability of the research, first of all, the interviews were carried out by a single researcher and the recorded audio files of the interviews were transcribed verbatim and their accuracy was confirmed by the participants. The answers to the questions were classified and thematic, descriptive and content analysis was carried out via NVIVO software. (Kelle, 1995; Cohen, Mannion & Morrison, 2007). At the end of the research, the findings were interpreted and discussed.

Findings

1. Factors affecting teachers' motivation

The factors affecting the motivation of the participants are shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Factors affecting teachers' motivation

Themes	Participants	f
Managers' approach	A, C, D	3
teacher environment	A, B, C, D	4
Working conditions of the school	D	1

As indicated in Table 2, the factors affecting the motivation of the participants were categorized under 3 sub-themes. When teachers were asked about the factors affecting their motivation, their answers were as follows:

'The factors that motivate us are of course the approach of the administrators. If such difficulties also help us, this affects us positively when we experience discomfort in transportation to and from the country.' (A)

'...good dialogue with my teacher friends and the motivation they and I add to them is the motivation they add to me, that is, we are smiling, on the one hand, we share the energy we give each other about the work we do...' (B)

'...my colleagues, school administration and students motivate me positively.' (C)

'The reason why I prefer my institution because the school is open in certain months, the education period is short, because I have a child, because I have a small baby...' (D)

As understood in thematic and descriptive analysis, the most important factor affecting the motivation of the participants was the teacher environment in the school. The teacher environment, which supported the school climate positively and strengthened the bond between teachers, strengthened the motivation of teachers. The approach of the administrators was in the second place among the factors affecting their motivation. Since the school type was a vocational high school, students did some of their internship periods when the school opens, and therefore the annual working time at the school was two months less than other schools.

2. Reasons for choosing the institution

The reasons why the participants preferred their institutions are shown in Table 3.

Table 3.

Reasons for choosing the institution

Themes	Participants	f
Vacancies	A, B	2
Foreign language proficiency	C	1
Less intensity of the lesson	D	1

As stated in Table 3, the reasons for choosing the institutions of the participants were categorized under 3 sub-themes. When the teachers were asked about their reasons for choosing the institution, different answers were received and they gave the following answers:

'The biggest reason for the vacant positions in the provincial appointment was the big vote, that is, because of the distance...' (A)

'The reason why I chose this institution is that foreign language courses are intensive.' (C)

'The reason why I prefer my institution, the school being open in certain months, the short education period, and the fact that I have a child...' (D)

As understood in thematic and descriptive analysis, the intensity of the course was increased in the months of November-May due to the internships of the students. Therefore, the reason for choosing the school was stated to be low course intensity. At the same time, teachers had difficulties in relocating because there were problems in the presence of vacancies in the province. The reason why the participants preferred their institutions was that there were vacant positions during the appointment

request period. The fact that the school was mainly on foreign language caused it to be preferred more by subject teachers. Teachers stated that they got more efficiency and affected their motivation positively.

3. Problems due to the travel to the institution

It was understood that the participants had many problems during transportation to school. Themes related to the difficulties experienced in transportation to school are shown in Table 4.

Table 4.

Problems due to the travel to the institution

Themes	Participants	f
Stress due to traffic density	A, B, C, D	4
Anxiety about not getting to school on time	D	1
Material influence	A, B, C	3
Distance	A, B, C, D	4
Problems with public transport	A, D	2
Waste of time	A, B, C, D	4
leaving home early	C	1

When we examined the themes in Table 4, the problems experienced by the teachers during transportation were grouped under 6 sub-themes. Teachers mentioned about the problems they encountered while travelling their institutions as follows:

'As I said I usually travel with my car, as I mentioned before, the biggest problem is the traffic density, the time spent in traffic is very long when we use the bus or public transport.'(A)

'...Especially in the morning and evening hours, the traffic density affects the most, and of course, it affects me negatively at this distance since it is far from where I live' (B)

'Because the place where our school is located is quite a distance from where I live, the bus does not depart frequently. That's why I have trouble reaching school, I can say that I'm often late'(D)

As understood in thematic and descriptive analysis, it was stated that teachers experienced stress about not being able to catch up with school, primarily due to traffic density. 3 of the teachers provided transportation with their own vehicle and 1 of them using public transportation vehicles. Teachers who used their own vehicles had more difficulty in travelling financially. Teachers who preferred public transportation, on the other hand, were negatively affected by the overcrowding of the bus, as well as the anxiety of catching the bus and catching the lesson. Some teachers, on the other hand, used public transport occasionally, while the majority of them travel with their own vehicles. As a result, most of the teachers who answered the questions saw the time spent on the road as a waste of time. One of the teachers stated that he left home 1 hour earlier because the traffic density was less.

4. Change in eating habits

As seen, it was stated that there were changes in the eating habits of the participants. Themes related to changes in eating habits are shown in Table 5.

Table 5.

Change in eating habits

Themes	Participants	f
No breakfast	A, B, C, D	4

Skipping main meals	A, B, C, D	4
Junk food nutrition	A	1
Not bringing your food with them	A, C	2

As indicated in Table 5, the findings related to the change in eating habits were categorized under 4 sub-themes and this question was answered by all the teachers. Teachers stated about the change in eating habits as follows:

'We do not have the opportunity to have breakfast in the morning, so we bring it with us most of the time. Lunch is also available in our school, but of course, we can say that it affects negatively because we eat more junk food.'(A)

'...we can't have our breakfast, we can't make enough preparations about it. We usually start the day without breakfast. Of course, I can say that I have a problem with food, since there are not many dining places around the school at noon.'(B)

'... Of course, lunch may not be healthy sometimes, so we can be affected by it.'(C)

'Eating habits are never at the forefront, I go out without even having breakfast because it is primarily to catch the bus, and I already take my food with me...'(D)

As understood in thematic and descriptive analysis, teachers stated that they got up very early to catch up with school and they could not have breakfast during the preparation phase. Since there was no place to eat around the school, some teachers also had trouble with lunch. The absence of main meals such as breakfast and lunch negatively affected teachers' eating habits and sometimes let them to eat junk food. Two teachers who participated in the interview stated that they prepared their breakfast and meals in the evening and that they ate what they brought with them during breaks or lunch breaks.

5. The effects of working in a distant place on family life

The effects of working in a distant place on the family life of the participants are shown in Table 6.

Table 6.

The effect of working in a distant place on family life

Themes	Participants	f
Leaving home early	A,B,C,D	4
Tiredness	A,C,D	3
Inability to catch up when there is an emergency	B, D	2
Inability to spend enough time with children	A,B,C,D	4
Dropping the child off to school early	A	1

Teachers expressed the effect of working in a distant place on their family life as follows:

'The biggest problem is of course being tired, there are too many children in the family after work, and one does not have much energy to spend time with him to play with him at work, it affects badly'(A)

'It affects my family life negatively. Because when they need me, I can't be right next to them. Today, for example, my child fell in the 2nd grade of primary school, his trousers were covered with mud, he had to change his clothes, but because my wife couldn't catch up, I had to run. I have trouble catching up with my family, especially when they are sick, I have to run again when there is an emergency, this distance really makes me tired'(B)

'Since most of our time is spent on the road, we may not be able to spare time for those at home sometimes.'(C)

'I am completely away from my family during the day. I can only see my family in the evening after work'(D)

As understood in thematic and descriptive analysis, the effects of working in a distant place on family life were categorized under 5 sub themes. Teachers had to leave home early in order to reach school. Leaving home early and coming home late due to the time spent on the road caused teachers to get tired and not be able to spend quality time with their children. In addition, the anxiety of not being able to catch up in case of an emergency due to the distance between school and home negatively affected teachers.

6. The effects of working in a distant place on professional life

The views of the participants on how working in a distant location affected their professional lives are given in Table 7.

Table 7.

The effects of working in a distant place on professional life

Themes	Participants	f
Deficiencies in lesson preparation	A, B	2
Inability to attend vocational courses	D	1
Deficiencies in personal development	C	1

In Table 7, the views on the effect of teachers who had too much distance between their home and school on their professional lives are given in 3 sub-themes. Teachers answered the question about the effects of working in a remote location on their professional life as follows:

'...Of course, we have some shortcomings in preparing lessons.'(B)

'We spend most of our time on the road, for example, we can bring it to the traffic at the time we will look at it, or we may have to spend the time that we will spare for ourselves in traffic.(C)

'I can't spare time for things like reading an extra course, an extra book in order to improve myself professionally'(D)

As understood in thematic and descriptive analysis, travelling teachers spent most of their time on the road, and these journeys prevented them from doing activities where they could improve themselves, such as preparing lessons, attending different courses related to their profession, or reading books. Teachers who came home tired preferred to spend their time resting more.

7. The financial impact of working in a remote place on the family budget

The participants were asked whether working in a distant place financially affected the family budget, and the findings are given in Table 8.

Table 8.

The financial impact of working in a remote place on the family budget

Themes	Participants	f
Yes, it negatively affects	A, B, C, D	4

As can be seen in Table 8, it was seen that the travels of the teachers working in a distant place affected them financially negatively. The answers given to the questions asked of teachers about whether working in a remote location affects them financially are as follows:

'Financially, of course, it is very tiring with the updated prices, so our fuel costs increase accordingly because it is far away' (A)

'...There is no person who is not affected by recent price increases, even at a close distance, and there is no financial benefit.' (B)

'Since we came with our private car, the road is long. Of course, the financial aspect of this also affects us.' (C)

'Inevitably, when I say food and travel fee, a certain amount of my own earnings goes there.' (D)

As understood in thematic and descriptive analysis affected all participants negatively, a single main theme was created. In particular, they stated that the increased oil costs affected their family budgets more negatively.

8. Inability to spare time for extracurricular activities due to working in a remote place

The participants were asked whether they could spare time for extracurricular social activities due to working in a distant place, and the findings are shown in Table 9.

Table 9.

Inability to spare time for extracurricular activities due to working in a remote place

Themes	Participants	f
I can't spare time on my working days	A, D	2
I can never participate in extracurricular activities because I am busy.	B	1
I rarely have time	D)	1

As seen in Table 4.8, it was found that teachers who were too far away from their home and the school they worked in had difficulties in allocating time for extracurricular activities. According to Table 4.8, there are 3 sub-themes. The teachers answered the question about allocating time for extracurricular activities as follows:

'...when we go home, we just want to rest, there is no time for any social activity...' (A)

'...I cannot do my extracurricular activities because my work is already busy, I just have to leave extracurricular activities at the weekend. I have reserved for myself a sports activity or a social activity, a cinema etc., unfortunately, no such social activity happens, extracurricular activities do not happen unfortunately' (B)

'Unfortunately, we can't spare time, because we leave late after school, this time we have responsibilities such as getting home and picking up the children from school' (C)

'You can't include any activities, it's tiring, I spend all day there, I can rarely do anything extra.' (D)

As understood in thematic and descriptive analysis, in addition to the teachers who stated that they could not spare time for extracurricular activities during working days, the teacher who worked as the vice principal stated that he could never participate in different activities. The teacher, whose course intensity was less than the others, stated that he rarely spared time for extracurricular activities.

9. Findings of Focus Group Interviews

Findings of working in a remote location as a parent

The participants were asked how working in a distant place as parents affected them, and the findings are shown in Table 10.

Table 10.

Findings of working in a remote location as a parent

Themes	Participants	f
I can't be there when my family needs me.	A, B, C, D	4
We are worried.	A	1

The answers to the question How working in a distant place as parents affected them are as follows:

'...of course, being away from the family, not being able to be there for them when they need us can be a big problem because when we need to take the child to us when he needs us, this distance can force us, aside from the financial aspect, in such a health situation, especially when it requires a quick intervention at that moment, we can worry. This situation can lead to...' (B)

'Reaching late when there is any problem with the health of children, of course, exposes us to stress'(A)

'...when we come to school, we cannot work in peace because we always have such thoughts in the back of our minds...' (C)

As seen in the themes and descriptive analysis in Table 10, working in a distant place and being unable to be there for their children and families when they needed them affected teachers negatively as parents and caused them to worry.

Findings of feelings before departure

The participants were asked about their feelings before the departure and the findings are shown in Table 11.

Table 11.

Findings of feelings before departure

Themes	Participants	f
I am experiencing stress.	A, B, C, D	4
I think about how my family will spend the day.	A	1
I'm in a hurry to catch the bus.	D	1
Traffic congestion is a problem.	C, D	2

In Table 11, the findings are categorized in themes according to the feelings of the teachers before they set out. Below are the answers to the question:

'The biggest problem for us is traffic, we are grateful if we can return home without any problems in traffic'(A)

'...I keep on my way thinking about both the school and the things I left behind, but of course the distance of the road and the worry that I will experience road stress on the other hand is always on our minds as we travel that road, because anything can happen in traffic at any moment, we meet very different people...' (B)

'I sometimes have to leave my children at home alone, leaving an hour in advance to get to school without being exposed to traffic'(C)

'Because I came to school by bus, I was in a hurry to catch the bus on time and get to school on time before I set off, so I set out with the idea of leaving school and family aside and reaching school first. Later when I come to school, when I get rid of that stress, when I reach school, I focus on the lesson, and when I focus on the lesson, this time I start to think about my family.'

As understood in thematic and descriptive analysis, teachers thought that they were stressed before they set off, thinking about both the road and the families they left behind, and also thinking that they would encounter heavy traffic on the road affects them negatively.

Findings related to belonging to the institution

The participants were asked whether working in a remote location affected their belonging to the institution, and the findings are shown in Table 12.

Table 12.

Findings related to belonging to the institution

Themes	Participants	f
It negatively affects my performance.	D	1
I am stressed, but I am at peace at school.	A,B,C,D	4

In Table 12, the answers given to the question about the teachers' belonging to the school were categorized in themes.

'Yes, it requires us to question here, sometimes I really come to this school, I come to this school. time, of course, these worries can go away.'(B)

'Working in an institution far from my home, while I can work more efficiently in a school closer to my home, inevitably affects my performance negatively.'(D)

As understood in thematic and descriptive analysis, teachers stated that they were happy at school, even though it was stressful for them when they were on the road. One teacher in the interview stated that it had a negative impact on his performance. They answered the question as follows:

Discussion and conclusion

The results of this study, which aimed to seek to understand the effects of teachers' motivations on their professional and personal lives, who were too far between the institution they worked and their residence address, are follows:

It was concluded that the fact that the teachers had to travel for different reasons, not in the environment where the school was located, affected the teachers negatively both professionally and individually. The travelling of the teachers brought with it different problems of its own. First, teachers woke up early in order to reach their school, there were two main reasons for this early wake up. The first was the concern of not being able to catch up with the school because the distance was too long, and the second was the undesirability of adding to the travel process when the traffic density was high. Considering the material and moral losses such as traveling, the stress experienced in traffic, the problems encountered during the journey, leaving home early and returning home late, it could be said that it was a very wearing process for teachers. The most important reason forcing teachers to travel was the lack of vacancies. The absence of schools with vacant positions in the regions where teachers' homes or spouses worked forced them to travel according to the assignment and relocation regulations. It was thought that the steps to be taken for the spouses to work in the same region would slightly improve this negative situation. It is seen that the findings obtained as a result of the research were parallel with the findings of Önen and Doğaner's (2017) study called 'The effects of working in an institution far from the place

of residence on the professional and private lives of teachers'. Some teachers, who were willing to travel, cannot find the working conditions of the school in other schools. The fact that students come from their internship at the end of November and go back to their internship at the end of April shortened the education period at the school about four months. This situation affected some teachers positively in continuing to work at school.

Due to the problems faced by teachers such as stress caused by the intensity experienced in traffic, fatigue, financial losses, anxiety about not being able to reach the stops for those who use public transport, physical and mental fatigue from the journey, difficulties in allocating time for himself and his family, the danger posed by climate and weather conditions, difficulties in reaching school in rainy weather, early setting off on time or even in the dark, and it's dangerous, teachers stated that their performances were negatively affected, their energy was low, they came to school tired and returned home tired, this caused their lack of nutrition, their motivation decreased, they could not spare time for themselves and their families, they could not enrich their personal and professional development, and they could not fully fulfill their roles as parents outside of working hours.

Teachers, who could not have enough time for themselves and their families, waited for the weekend to do their private work outside of school, but even this was not enough. Especially teachers working as managers had more difficulties in this regard. Teachers, who could not spare time for themselves, wanted to attend in-service courses related to their profession to contribute to their personal development, but they were tired because of their workload and long journeys. Due to this fatigue, they could not participate in any activity or course.

It is obvious that teachers were adversely affected financially and morally because of their travelling to their schools. Teachers who had to pay higher fares while travelling than teachers working in the region where they lived suffered from this situation. In particular, the increase in oil prices with each passing day affected family budgets more. This situation hampered the passion of teachers to go to work and affected their whole lives.

As a result, teachers' travelling for years affected them negatively. The most important reason why teachers had low motivation in both their professional and private lives was that they could not spend the time themselves, their families and students as they spent most of their times on travelling. The problems encountered during the time spent on travelling disturbed the teachers in family and professional matters.

Recommendations

In consistent with the results obtained, following suggestions can be put forward:

1. In assignments for disability groups, spouses should be assigned to regions close to their workplaces within the boundaries of the same region or based on a certain km limit.
2. This research was carried out a single district and school. More quantitative and qualitative studies can be done in this subject.
3. Shuttle service can be provided for teachers who travel.
4. An extra road fee may be added to the salaries of travelling teachers as having an extra road fee or shuttle service can relax and encourage teachers.

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Ethical Approval

In the writing process of the study titled “**The effect of the motivations of teachers who are working in the institution far from their residence address on their professional and private lives**”, the rules of scientific, ethical and citation were followed; it was undertaken by the authors of this study that no falsification was made on the collected data. “Journal Action Qualitative & Mixed Methods Research [JAQMER] and Editor” had no responsibility for all ethical violations to be encountered, and all responsibility belongs to the authors and that the study was not submitted for evaluation to any other academic publishing environment.

Ethics Committee Approval

Ethics Committee Approval of this research was obtained from Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the meeting of 14 decision numbered 377 on November 4th, 2021.